

INTRODUCTION OF INNOVATION IN CHEMISTRY CLASSES

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Abstract: This article mentions the need for the timely use of modern pedagogical technologies and a wide range of moves in the course of the lesson, and sets out a number of tasks.

Keywords: chemistry, bodies, synthetics, history of development.

At the same time, a stream of information is entering the social life of the Republic at a violent pace and is covering a wide range. Receiving information at a fast pace, analyzing, processing, theoretically generalizing, inference and establishing student-student delivery are some of the pressing challenges facing the educational system. The introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process serves to positively solve the above-mentioned urgent problem. One of the factors of the successful application of pedagogical technologies in the educational process is the preliminary design of a certain holistic educational process, the diagnosis of the level of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by students, and the ability to predict the successful outcome of the educational goal from the very beginning. Technology (Greek. "techne" – skill, art, "logos" – concept, doctrine) - specific (production, social, economic, etc.) the organization of processes at the level of high skill, art. The central problem of educational technology is to ensure the achievement of the educational goal through the development of the personality of the student.

Educational Technology (Eng. "an educational technology") is the organization of the educational (teaching) process at the level of high skill, art. Educational technology is the general content of the process of achieving the educational goal, that is, the implementation of the previously designed educational process on the basis of a holistic system, step by step, the development of a system of certain methods, methods and tools on the way to a specific goal, their effective, productive use and a high level of management of the educational process:

When designing the educational process, the system will not work if any of the above elements are ignored or incorrectly selected, it means that the goal set before the educational process will not be achieved. Organization of education-the external manifestation of the paths of joint activities of the teacher and student in the educational process. In the case of a method-path, the form is the exterior of the path. Currently, modern methods of teaching are widely used in the educational process. The application of modern teaching methods leads to the achievement of high efficiency in the teaching process. When choosing educational methods, it is considered advisable to choose based on the didactic task of each lesson. In mastering the content of education, the following variants of methods are used, which are divided into three groups, depending on the level of knowledge of students, their ability to master, the source of Education, didactic tasks, appropriately verbal, visual and practical:

- lecture (interview) method of teaching; -
- method of practical work of teaching;
- method of laboratory work; - method of independent work;
- problematic-heuristic modeling method;
- research methods;
- problematic-research and reproductive method of training;
- inductive and deductive method of teaching;
- the method of control and self-control of training.

While maintaining the traditional lesson form, enriching it with different methods that activate the activities of students leads to an increase in the level of student assimilation. This requires a rational organization of the lesson process, constant stimulation by the teacher of students' activity in the educational process, mental attack in the process of breaking the educational material into small pieces and revealing their content, work in small groups, controversy, problem situation, using techniques such as referral text, Project, role-playing games and encouraging students to independently perform practical exercises.

The issue of organizing, managing and educating a harmonious personality of the younger generation is gaining more relevance in a situation where new views are being decided in the social life of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Achieving high quality and efficiency in the educational process requires an innovative approach to the educational process. The term "innovation" is derived from the English word "innovation", meaning "innovate", "new idea". In innovative teaching, the task of knowledge changes. That is, from the previous constant memorization, logical thinking goes to the search. Such activity develops creativity in the student's activities. He enters into a mutually active "subject-subject" relationship with his peers and teacher. Due to the fact that the teaching process is dynamic and a solid facade, it is also natural for it to be innovated and the practice of renewal to continue. Therefore, it is necessary to apply modern technologies that are tested and effective. The most common and characteristic modern pedagogical technologies in the teaching of Chemistry are considered to be: conversation, argument, play, case-stick, method of projects, problem method, mental attack, etc. Debate (debate) is an active method of exchange of views on a specific problem, teaching in the form of discussion.

The discussion method performs all tasks this method is used for the following purposes:

- ❖ in the formation of new knowledge;
- ❖ in order for readers to think deeply about one or another question, to provide access to their essence;
- ❖ in teaching students to understand the difference between evidence and evidence-based inferences, the;
- ❖ space in the formation of mutual thought exchange skills;
- ❖ to help students stand firm in their personal opinion and protect the moment.

The debate is free, when it develops freely, it can be manageable. It should apply only to topics and questions that need to be mastered.

Insert is an interactive system of marking in text for effective reading and thinking. Application treatment of questions to activate previous knowledge and mark it in the text. After that, the designation of information of each type, which occurs in the text.

Insert is a powerful tool that allows the learner to actively monitor his independent

learning in the process of working with text.

Insert is a teaching method used to solve the complex tasks of mastering and strengthen the educational material, develop the educational qualifications of working with a book.

"Mental attack" is derived from the English word "breynstorming" (brain storming), one of the techniques of Active Education, Management and research. This method provokes mental activity, accelerates creative and innovative processes. A pinboard (from English: pin - fastening, board - writing board) consists of matching discussion methods or training conversation with a practical method. Educational game business and role (status) Lee games are a type of problematic assignment. Only in this case, instead of textual material, staged life situations are used, which are played by readers. In the teaching of Chemistry, a huge number of modern educational technologies are effectively used. We will get acquainted with the description of some of them and their application in the teaching of chemistry. The blitz-survey method establishes a psychological communicative link between those surveyed. Questions are drawn up in advance by the interrogator. Questions require a short specific answer. In this method, students are offered in the form of answers (oral, written, table, diagram) to questions formulated on the basic concepts and base phrases of the entire topic studied and a certain part of it.

Procedure for conducting training:

- the teacher divides the students into subgroups of 3-5K depending on the number of subjects (it is desirable that the number of groups is 4 or 5); 21
 - students are introduced to the purpose of the training and the order in which it is conducted. To each group, on the left side of the paper, sheets with a small topic inscription are distributed;
 - the teacher gives the task of group members to familiarize themselves with small topics written in the disseminated material and, using a felt-tip pen what they know on the basis of this topic, to write together with the team to a blank space on paper and set a time;
 - the members of the group together express a small subject given in the dissemination material in the form of writing (or painting, or drawing). In doing so, the group members will have to provide as complete information as possible on a small topic.
 - When the distribution material is filled, one person from the group members makes a presentation. The materials prepared by the groups at the time of the presentation will definitely be attached to the class board logically tagma-tag (in the form of a chain);
- The teacher comments on the materials prepared by the groups, evaluates them and completes the training.

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